

A Hybrid Architecture for Fast Frequent Itemset Mining

Swet Mrigank

Abstract

Frequent itemset mining is a core primitive for market-basket analysis, product bundling, recommendation, cross-selling, and co-occurrence discovery. Practical deployments face two persistent challenges: classical Apriori-style mining becomes slow at low support thresholds, and higher-order itemset enumeration suffers from rapid combinatorial growth.

We present *fastapriori*, a Python-facing frequent itemset mining library backed by a Rust engine. The system uses a hybrid inverted-index architecture: for $k = 2$, it exhaustively counts pairwise co-occurrences using a shared inverted index and computes association metrics in a post-count pass; for $k \geq 3$, it switches to anchor-and-extend support counting using frequent $(k-1)$ -itemsets as anchors and a pairwise downward-closure filter. The design is motivated by the observation that, after singleton filtering, Apriori-style pruning provides little benefit for pair counting but becomes important for higher-order itemsets. The algorithmic ingredients (inverted indexes, exhaustive pair counting, anchor-based extension, dirty-list scatter) have precedents in vertical mining and optimized pair-counting work; the contribution here is the engineered hybrid, the deployed implementation, and a regime characterization against optimized C/Python baselines.

Across 18 real and synthetic datasets and 4,891 valid configurations, *fastapriori* consistently outperforms a same-codebase Rust Apriori baseline for pairwise mining (100% of $k=2$ cells, median speedup 27× at the lowest tested support) and is substantially faster on most higher-order configurations (96.8% of completed $k \geq 3$ cells, median speedup 15.6×). Against optimized PyFIM/Borgelt implementations, *fastapriori* is strongest for pairwise and large sparse workloads – wins 94.4% of lowest-support $k=2$ cells against the median PyFIM variant (median speedup 2.4×) and 83.3% against the best PyFIM variant – while Eclat and FP-Growth remain competitive or superior on narrow, dense, high-skew higher-order workloads (only 24.6% / 16.7% $k \geq 3$ wins against PyFIM median / best). On the three largest synthetic workloads (20 M–125 M rows), *fastapriori* completes pairwise mining 2.0–2.8× faster (median 2.4×) than the best tested PyFIM/Borgelt variant on a single Google Cloud c3-highmem-8 VM; the regime characterization is supported by an exploratory XGBoost classifier (stratified-CV MCC 0.94, leave-one-dataset-out AUROC 0.88).

1 Introduction

Frequent itemset mining is a foundational technique in data mining, with applications in market-basket analysis, retail assortment planning, recommendation systems, product bundling, cross-selling, healthcare co-morbidity analysis, and industrial parts analysis. Since the introduction of Apriori by Agrawal and Srikant [1], the central algorithmic principle has been **downward closure**: if an itemset is infrequent, then all of its supersets must also be infrequent.

This principle enables level-wise mining. First, frequent singleton items are found. Then candidate pairs are generated from those

items. Frequent pairs generate candidate triples, and so on. At each level, candidates whose subsets are infrequent can be pruned.

Despite its elegance, classical Apriori has two practical weaknesses.

First, at low support thresholds, many candidates survive. The pruning advantage weakens, but the costs of candidate generation, subset checking, hashing, and repeated support counting remain.

Second, higher-order mining grows rapidly with k . Even when pruning is effective, the number of potential itemsets can become large, especially for dense or highly correlated datasets.

These weaknesses matter because low support is often required in real applications. In a large e-commerce catalog, rare but valuable co-occurrences may involve premium products, seasonal items, new launches, specialty SKUs, replacement parts, or rare medications. A support threshold that is too high may remove the long-tail associations that motivated the analysis in the first place.

This paper presents *fastapriori*, a Python package with a compiled Rust backend designed for low-support frequent itemset mining (with full association-rule metrics emitted as a $k=2$ post-count pass). The system uses one shared inverted-index architecture for both pairwise and higher-order mining:

- At $k = 2$, *fastapriori* counts co-occurrences exhaustively using a transaction-to-items and item-to-transactions representation.
- At $k \geq 3$, it switches to an anchor-and-extend strategy that uses frequent $(k-1)$ -itemsets as anchors and applies a pairwise downward-closure filter (necessary, not sufficient at $k \geq 4$) to reduce candidate expansion.

The design follows a simple principle: *use exhaustive counting where pruning provides little benefit, and use pruning where the candidate space becomes combinatorial*.

The paper evaluates this design empirically across real and synthetic datasets and compares it against optimized external baselines.

1.1 Why Low Support Matters

A common objection to low-support mining is that thresholds such as 10^{-3} or 10^{-4} are too small to be useful. In large datasets, however, these thresholds can correspond to hundreds or thousands of transactions.

For example, on the Instacart grocery dataset [15] with ~3.2 million transactions (Table 1), a support threshold of 10^{-3} corresponds to approximately 3,200 transactions; a threshold of 10^{-4} still corresponds to approximately 320 transactions. In commercial or scientific settings, an itemset occurring a few hundred times may be operationally meaningful.

Low support is especially important in long-tail catalogs. Retail, e-commerce, clickstream, and industrial datasets often contain a small number of extremely common items and a long tail of less frequent but still important items. Classical Apriori forces the support threshold into the counting process itself: if the threshold is set too high, the tail disappears; if set too low, candidate explosion can dominate runtime.

Table 1: Real-world benchmark datasets. “Long-format rows” denotes transaction-item pairs ($\sum_t |T_t| = D \cdot d_{\text{avg}}$), not transactions; “Items” is the catalog size N and “Txns” the transaction count D . d_{avg} is the average basket size, d_{max} the maximum basket size, $\tau = d_{\text{max}}/d_{\text{avg}}$ the tail ratio, and $d_{\text{CV}} = \sigma_d/d_{\text{avg}}$ the coefficient of variation of transaction sizes.

Dataset	Domain	Long-fmt rows	Items	Txns	d_{avg}	d_{max}	τ	d_{CV}
Groceries [11]	Grocery	43K	169	9,835	4.4	32	7.3	0.81
BMS-WebView-1 [10]	Clickstream	150K	497	59,602	2.5	267	106.8	1.93
BMS-WebView-2 [10]	Clickstream	358K	3,340	77,512	4.6	161	35.0	1.31
Retail (Belgian) [6]	Retail	909K	16,470	88,162	10.3	76	7.4	0.79
Online Retail [8]	E-commerce	525K	4,632	28,816	18.2	675	37.1	1.92
Kosarak [10]	Clickstream	8.0M	41,270	990,002	8.1	2,498	308.4	2.91
Chainstore [10]	Chain store	8.0M	46,086	1,112,949	7.2	170	23.6	1.23
Instacart [15]	Grocery	32.4M	49,677	3,214,874	10.1	145	14.4	0.74

Several analytical use-cases require operating in exactly this low-support regime. Anomaly and fraud detection target rare co-occurrence patterns [7] – a fraudulent transaction triple may appear in only a few hundred of millions of records, yet matter disproportionately. Defect-co-occurrence mining in manufacturing, adverse-event analysis in pharmacovigilance [13], rare-disease co-morbidity studies [14], and root-cause analysis from telemetry logs all share this structure: the relevant signal lives below $s \sim 10^{-3}$ on large datasets, where high-support filtering would discard it before it can be examined. For these workloads, a method whose cost is approximately constant in s is not just a performance win – it is what makes the analysis tractable at all.

For pairwise mining, *fastapriori* avoids this trade-off by counting all pairwise co-occurrences first and applying the support threshold only as a final filter. This makes pairwise runtime approximately independent of the support threshold for a fixed dataset.

1.2 Contributions

This paper makes three main contributions.

1.2.1 Systems Architecture. We describe a hybrid inverted-index architecture for frequent itemset mining. The same index supports (1) exhaustive pair counting at $k = 2$, and (2) anchor-and-extend mining with a pairwise downward-closure filter at $k \geq 3$.

The pair-counting phase uses flat arrays and sparse dirty-list extraction to avoid scanning a full item-by-item matrix after each anchor item.

1.2.2 Empirical Benchmark. We evaluate *fastapriori* on 18 datasets, including 8 real-world and 10 synthetic datasets. The benchmark contains 4,891 valid configurations (method-dataset- k -support cells where the run completed) over multiple support thresholds and itemset sizes.

We compare against:

- CLASSIC: a same-codebase Rust Apriori implementation,
- PYFIM: Borgelt’s C implementations of Apriori, Eclat, and FP-Growth exposed through Python [5],
- Borgelt command-line binaries,
- EA (*efficient-apriori* [20]): a standard Python Apriori implementation.

The same-codebase comparison isolates the effect of the hybrid counting strategy from language and runtime effects. The external

baselines evaluate practical competitiveness against established implementations.

1.2.3 Regime Characterization. We show that *fastapriori* is especially strong for pairwise mining and for large sparse workloads. For higher-order mining, performance is regime-dependent: Eclat [25] and FP-Growth [12] remain strong on narrow, dense, or highly correlated datasets. We therefore present a preliminary data-shape-based decision rule for selecting between methods. An XGBoost classifier trained on 19 features reaches Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) = 0.94 for fast-vs-PyFIM and MCC = 0.79 for fast-vs-classic under stratified 5-fold cross-validation, with leave-one-dataset-out area under the ROC curve (AUROC) of 0.88 and 0.91 respectively confirming that the ranking generalises to unseen datasets.

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Apriori and Downward Closure

Apriori [1] introduced the anti-monotonicity principle for support-based frequent itemset mining. If an itemset is not frequent, no superset of that itemset can be frequent. This allows candidate itemsets to be generated level by level and pruned before support counting.

Apriori remains conceptually simple and widely used, but its performance depends strongly on the support threshold and the number of surviving candidates. At low support, candidate generation and support counting can become expensive.

2.2 Pattern-Growth Methods

FP-Growth [12] avoids explicit candidate generation by compressing the transaction database into an FP-tree and recursively mining conditional pattern bases. This can be highly effective on datasets with shared prefixes or dense repeated structure.

The proposed method does not use an FP-tree. Instead, it uses flat arrays and inverted lists, favoring memory locality and a simpler compiled implementation.

2.3 Vertical Mining and Eclat

Eclat [25] represents each item by a transaction-ID list and mines frequent itemsets by intersecting these lists. This vertical representation is closely related to the inverted index used in *fastapriori*.

A related approach is Bodon’s trie-based Apriori [3], which uses a direct array for $k = 2$ support counting; the same array trick is used by Borgelt’s `PFIM_apriori` at $k = 2$.

The difference is operational. Eclat typically performs depth-first recursive tid-list intersections. *fastapriori* uses a breadth-oriented inverted-index approach: exhaustive co-occurrence counting at $k = 2$, followed by anchor-and-extend counting at higher levels. Table 2 positions the methods on the (traversal \times data layout) grid. We use “Horizontal” for methods that scan the database transaction-by-transaction and “Vertical” for methods that maintain a per-item TID-list. AprioriTID [1] propagates TID-lists across levels and is therefore BFS-Vertical. Bodon’s trie-based Apriori [3] sits in BFS-Horizontal because the trie stores candidate itemsets, not TID-lists; the underlying database scan is still horizontal.

Table 2: Frequent-itemset mining methods by traversal and data layout.

	Horizontal	Vertical
BFS	Apriori [1]; DHP [19]; trie-Apriori [3]	AprioriTID [1]; Counter+chain (this paper)
DFS	—	Eclat [25]
Tree	—	FP-growth [12]

Thus, the proposed method should be viewed as part of the broader family of vertical and hybrid frequent-itemset mining approaches, rather than as a fundamentally new pruning paradigm.

2.4 Optimized Implementations

Several mature implementations exist, including Borgelt’s Apriori, Eclat, and FP-Growth implementations [5], the `PFIM` Python bindings, *mlxtend* [21], *EA* [20], and *SPMF* [10].

This work focuses on a practical Python-facing system with a Rust backend and a regime-aware benchmark against optimized C and Python baselines.

2.5 Low-Support and Rare-Itemset Mining

Standard frequent-itemset mining uses a single global support threshold s_{\min} and discards everything below it. When the patterns of interest are inherently rare – fraud, adverse drug reactions, defect co-occurrences, rare-disease comorbidities (§1.1) – a high s_{\min} removes the signal before mining begins, but a low s_{\min} on a single global threshold causes Apriori-style candidate explosion on the common items. The rare-itemset literature addresses this tension through algorithmic redesign rather than implementation tuning. Borah and Nath [4] survey roughly 50 variants in two main families.

Multiple minimum supports. *MSApriori* (Liu et al. [18]) and its descendants assign each item its own support threshold based on prior information about expected frequency, allowing rare items to participate in mining without dragging down the threshold for common items. The trade-off is that the user must supply or estimate per-item thresholds.

Apriori-Inverse and sporadic rules. Koh and Rountree [16] flip the support condition to explicitly target itemsets that occur *rarely* but with high confidence (sporadic rules). The algorithmic structure is still level-wise candidate generation, but the pruning direction is inverted.

Domain-specific methods. In pharmacovigilance, disproportionality analysis on FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (AERS) spontaneous reports combines association rule mining with statistical tests for unexpected co-occurrence [13]. In disease co-morbidity studies, the analysis often runs at a fixed low support across millions of patient records [14]. These domain methods sit *on top* of a frequent-itemset miner; the choice of miner determines whether s can be pushed low enough for the rare patterns of interest.

Where *fastapriori* fits. The methods above all share a structural property: they specify *which* rare patterns to keep, not *how* to enumerate frequent pairs or itemsets efficiently. Multi-threshold pruning, sporadic-rule conditions, and disproportionality tests sit on top of a frequent-itemset miner that produces co-occurrence counts at low support; the choice of underlying miner determines whether the threshold can be pushed low enough to surface rare signal at all. *fastapriori* is designed to be that substrate: at $k = 2$, its runtime is approximately independent of s (cost model §3.7.1), and at $k = 3$ anchor-and-extend with cross-level intersection memoization keeps the per-anchor work proportional to $|\text{txn}(\sigma)| \cdot d_{\text{avg}}$, which is small for rare anchors by construction. Rare-itemset techniques therefore compose with *fastapriori* rather than compete with it – they are not different pair-counters, and we do not benchmark against them, because the comparison would be against a different workload (filter specification) rather than against a faster way of producing the same frequent-pair output.

3 Algorithm

3.1 Problem Definition

Let $\mathcal{D} = \{T_1, T_2, \dots, T_D\}$ be a transaction database over an item universe \mathcal{I} of size N (Agrawal and Srikant’s convention [1], also matching the Quest synthetic generator parameters in Table 3). Each transaction T_t is a set of items. The input is represented as a table of transaction-item pairs (t, i) ; the long-format size is $\sum_{t=1}^D |T_t| = D \cdot d_{\text{avg}}$.

For an itemset $S \subseteq \mathcal{I}$, the support count is $c(S) = |\{t : S \subseteq T_t\}|$, and the support is $\text{support}(S) = c(S)/D$. Given a minimum support threshold s_{\min} , an itemset S is frequent if $c(S) \geq \lceil s_{\min} D \rceil$.

For $k = 2$, *fastapriori* computes pairwise association metrics including support, confidence, lift, conviction, leverage, cosine similarity, and Jaccard index. For $k \geq 3$, the system enumerates *frequent itemsets* along with one rule of the form $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}) \rightarrow c$ per itemset (support, confidence, and lift). The full set of antecedent/consequent splits is computable as a downstream post-processing pass over the returned frequent itemsets and is out of scope for this paper; the architectural and benchmark contributions concern itemset support counting.

3.2 Shared Inverted-Index Representation

Both *fastapriori* and the same-codebase Apriori baseline begin by building a shared index in a single pass over the transaction-item table.

Algorithm 1 FAST-COUNT-PAIRS: Exhaustive pairwise counting via inverted index. Items below min_count (infrequent singletons) are filtered from \mathcal{I} before the pair-counting loop; this is the only downward-closure pruning applied at $k = 2$.

Require: Database \mathcal{D} with D transactions, N unique items, support threshold s_{min}

Ensure: Map of frequent pairs $\{(A, B) \rightarrow \text{count}\}$

```

1: (txn_to_items, item_to_txns) ← BUILD-INDEX( $\mathcal{D}$ )                                ▷  $O(D \cdot d_{avg})$  single pass
2:  $min\_count \leftarrow \lceil s_{min} \cdot D \rceil$ 
3:  $counts \leftarrow$  array of  $N$  zeros                                          ▷ reusable flat buffer, one slot per item
4:  $result \leftarrow$  empty map;  $dirty \leftarrow$  empty list
5: for each item  $A \in \mathcal{I}$  do
6:   for each transaction  $t \in \text{item\_to\_txns}(A)$  do
7:     for each item  $B \in \text{txn\_to\_items}(t)$  do
8:       if  $counts[B] = 0$  then append  $B$  to  $dirty$ 
9:        $counts[B] \leftarrow counts[B] + 1$ 
10:  for each  $B \in dirty$  do                                                  ▷ sparse extraction in  $O(|dirty|) \leq O(D \cdot d_{avg})$ 
11:    if  $counts[B] \geq min\_count$  and  $B > A$  then
12:       $result[(A, B)] \leftarrow counts[B]$ 
13:     $counts[B] \leftarrow 0$ 
14:   $dirty \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
15: return  $result$ 

```

The index contains:

- (1) txn_to_items : a mapping from each transaction to its sorted list of items,
- (2) $item_to_txns$: a mapping from each item to the sorted list of transactions containing it,
- (3) $item_counts$: the frequency of each item.

Items are remapped to dense integer IDs before mining. Transactions are deduplicated and sorted. The index is stored using flat arrays where possible to reduce object overhead and improve cache locality.

3.3 Pairwise Mining: Exhaustive Co-occurrence Counting

At $k = 2$, *fastapriori* counts co-occurrences directly (Algorithm 1).

For each item A , the algorithm scans the transactions containing A . For each such transaction, it increments a count buffer for every item B appearing in that transaction. After all transactions containing A have been processed, the algorithm extracts all pairs (A, B) whose counts meet the support threshold.

The support threshold is applied only during extraction. Therefore, for a fixed dataset, the main counting work does not depend on s_{min} .

Implementation note: dirty-list sparse scatter. A textbook implementation of the extraction step would scan the full N -slot count buffer once per anchor item, paying $O(N^2)$ overall. Our deployed implementation replaces this scan with a *dirty list* that records exactly the slots touched during co-occurrence increments for the current anchor; extraction iterates only those slots rather than the full buffer. The dominant counting work is $\Theta(\sum_{t=1}^D |T_t|^2)$, since each transaction contributes to the co-occurrence counts of all pairs of its items. When transaction lengths concentrate around d_{avg} , this is approximately $\Theta(D \cdot d_{avg}^2)$; when transaction lengths are highly skewed, the $\sum_t |T_t|^2$ form is more accurate. The total extraction cost $\sum_A |dirty(A)|$ is bounded above by the number of distinct

co-occurring item pairs (at most $O(N^2)$ in the fully-dense limit) and below by the count of *touched* co-occurrence slots; in practice, on the sparse datasets considered here, it tracks $\Theta(\sum_t |T_t|^2)$ closely and stays well below the worst-case bound.

3.4 Higher-Order Mining: Anchor-and-Extend

For $k \geq 3$, exhaustive counting becomes expensive. *fastapriori* therefore switches to an anchor-and-extend strategy (Algorithm 2). At level k , each frequent $(k-1)$ -itemset acts as an anchor. The algorithm finds transactions supporting that anchor and counts possible extension items within those transactions. The candidate itemset $S = \sigma \cup \{c\}$ is retained if its support count exceeds the threshold and it passes the downward-closure filter. The deployed implementation uses a *pairwise downward-closure filter*: every pair (a, c) for $a \in \sigma$ is verified against the frequent-pair set P in $O(k)$ time, which is cheaper than the full $(k-1)$ -subset check while retaining most of its pruning power.

The recursion is initialized at level $k = 2$ by setting $anchor_tids_2[\{i\}] = \text{item_to_txns}[i]$ for each frequent singleton, derived from the same inverted index that powers Algorithm 1. The key efficiency property is that σ_{tids} on line 3 is read from the previous level's cache instead of being rebuilt from $\binom{|t|}{k-1}$ subset enumerations across all transactions; the per-level work therefore becomes linear in $|F_{k-1}|$ rather than combinatorial in transaction width.

Deployed implementation details. The conceptual algorithm above is the deployed Rust implementation, augmented with:

- dense `Vec<u32>` TID-list storage for small sets, swapped to `RoaringBitmap` [17] above 32 elements to amortise intersection cost across density regimes,
- Rayon-based parallelism over anchors when their count exceeds a threshold of 500,
- per-thread count buffers,
- first-write-wins deduplication during the per-thread result merge (safe because support is itemset-invariant: any path to the

Algorithm 2 FAST-ANCHOR-EXTEND: k -itemset counting with cross-level intersection memoization

Require: Frequent $(k-1)$ -sets F_{k-1} , cached anchor TID-lists from previous level $anchor_tids_{k-1}$, frequent-pair set P , transaction-to-items map txn_to_items , item-to-transactions map $item_to_txns$, N items, min_count

Ensure: Map of k -set counts $result$, cached anchor TID-lists $anchor_tids_k$ for next level

- 1: $result \leftarrow$ empty map; $anchor_tids_k \leftarrow$ empty map
- 2: **for** each anchor $\sigma \in F_{k-1}$ **do**
- 3: $\sigma_{tids} \leftarrow anchor_tids_{k-1}[\sigma]$ ▷ memoized; not re-enumerated
- 4: $counts \leftarrow$ empty sparse counter; $dirty \leftarrow$ empty list
- 5: **for** each $t \in \sigma_{tids}$ **do**
- 6: **for** each item $c \in txn_to_items[t] \setminus \sigma$ **do**
- 7: **if** $counts[c] = 0$ **then** append c to $dirty$
- 8: $counts[c] \leftarrow counts[c] + 1$
- 9: **for** each $c \in dirty$ **do**
- 10: **if** $counts[c] \geq min_count$ **then**
- 11: $S \leftarrow \text{SORT}(\sigma \cup \{c\})$
- 12: **if** $S \notin result$ **and** PAIRS-FREQUENT(S, P) **then**
- 13: $new_tids \leftarrow \sigma_{tids} \cap item_to_txns[c]$ ▷ cache for level $k+1$
- 14: $result[S] \leftarrow counts[c]$
- 15: $anchor_tids_k[S] \leftarrow new_tids$
- 16: $counts[c] \leftarrow 0$
- 17: **return** ($result, anchor_tids_k$)

same sorted itemset S produces the same count, so the pairwise downward-closure filter never drops a different count for S).

The pairwise downward-closure filter – requiring every pair (a, c) for $a \in \sigma$ to be in P – is used as a cheap pruning heuristic, not for correctness. Correctness of the output follows from direct support counting on the candidate itemsets, not from the filter; the filter is necessary at $k = 3$ (equivalent to full downward closure) and a strict subset of full downward closure for $k \geq 4$, so it can let through non-frequent candidates that the support count then rejects.

3.5 The Classic Algorithm

To enable a like-for-like algorithmic comparison, we implement a faithful Rust port of Apriori sharing the same inverted-index builder and Rayon parallelism infrastructure as Algorithm 1; full pseudocode in App. C (Algorithm 3). The implementation does standard level-wise candidate generation (join + prune) and counts support per candidate via *short-circuit intersection*: sort items by frequency ascending, initialise *current* to the rarest item’s transaction list, and intersect remaining items in turn; if $|current| < min_count$ at any point, return \perp early. The short-circuit helps at high support but becomes largely ineffective at low support.

3.6 Hybrid Counting Strategy

The architectural claim of this paper is that pruning should be used only where it reduces work. At $k = 2$, candidate generation adds overhead without meaningful benefit, so exhaustive counting is preferable. At $k \geq 3$, the frequent $(k-1)$ -sets provide useful structure for pruning, so a hybrid approach becomes advantageous. Our system adopts exactly this division.

3.7 Cost Model

This section presents implementation-oriented cost models rather than implementation-independent theoretical lower bounds; the empirical regime map of §5.2 and §6.3 is the load-bearing claim, with the cost expressions below as a mechanistic explanation.

3.7.1 Pairwise Cost Model. For pairwise mining, FAST performs one inverted-index build followed by exhaustive co-occurrence counting. The dominant cost is

$$W_{\text{fast}}(2) = \Theta\left(\sum_{t=1}^D |T_t|^2\right) + \mathcal{O}\left(\sum_A |\text{dirty}(A)|\right) + \mathcal{O}(D \cdot d_{\text{avg}}),$$

where the first term is the co-occurrence counting work, the second is the sparse-extraction sweep over only the slots touched during counting (bounded above by $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ in the dense limit but empirically far smaller on the sparse benchmarks below), and $\mathcal{O}(D \cdot d_{\text{avg}})$ is the inverted-index build. For a fixed dataset this cost is approximately independent of the support threshold because all pair counts are computed before filtering.

In contrast, a classical Apriori implementation first filters singleton items and then generates candidate pairs from frequent singletons. Let $\ell(s)$ be the number of frequent singleton items at support threshold s , and let $\overline{W}_{\text{intersect}}(s)$ denote the average cost of a single short-circuited pair-support intersection. The dominant cost at $k = 2$ is

$$W_{\text{classic}}(2, s) = \mathcal{O}(N) + \binom{\ell(s)}{2} \cdot \overline{W}_{\text{intersect}}(s),$$

where the $\mathcal{O}(N)$ term accounts for the singleton-frequency pass. As s decreases, both $\ell(s)$ and $\overline{W}_{\text{intersect}}(s)$ are typically non-decreasing (short-circuit becomes less effective), so $W_{\text{classic}}(2, s)$ is expected

to grow as $s \rightarrow 0^+$. As $s \rightarrow 0^+$, $\ell(s) \rightarrow N$ and, under a uniform-frequency approximation, the limiting cost approaches $\binom{N}{2} \cdot \Theta(2D \cdot d_{\text{avg}}/N) = (N-1) \cdot D \cdot d_{\text{avg}}$.

Comparing the two: $W_{\text{fast}}(2)$ is approximately constant in s , while $W_{\text{classic}}(2, s)$ is expected to grow as $s \rightarrow 0^+$. On every dataset in our benchmark, $N \gg d_{\text{avg}}$ (ratios from 38 \times on Groceries to 6,405 \times on Chainstore), so the cost expressions predict a low-support regime where exhaustive pair counting outperforms candidate-generation pair mining. Empirically this crossover sits above the highest support we tested (10^{-2}) on every dataset: FAST(2) wins all 18 datasets against CLASSIC at every $s \in [10^{-4}, 10^{-2}]$, with the median speedup growing from $\sim 5\text{--}7\times$ at $s = 10^{-2}$ to $\sim 27\times$ at $s = 10^{-4}$. The exact crossover support s^* depends on constant factors, item-frequency skew, transaction-length skew, and cache effects, so we treat the cost expressions as implementation-guiding heuristics rather than a formal dominance argument.

3.7.2 Higher-Order Cost Model. At $k \geq 3$, both exhaustive and pruning-based methods can become expensive.

For Apriori, the dominant costs are joining frequent $(k-1)$ -itemsets to form candidate k -itemsets, pruning candidates, and counting support for each surviving candidate. A simplified expression is

$$W_{\text{classic}}(k) \approx \mathcal{O}(|F_{k-1}|^2 \cdot W_{\text{join}}) + \mathcal{O}(|C_k| \cdot W_{\text{count}}).$$

For FAST’s anchor-and-extend method (Algorithm 2), the dominant costs are constructing or retrieving anchor-support transaction lists, scanning transactions supporting each anchor, and counting extension items. A simplified expression is

$$W_{\text{fast}}(k) \approx \mathcal{O}(W_{\text{anchor-map}}) + \mathcal{O}\left(\sum_{\sigma \in F_{k-1}} \sum_{t \in \text{supp}(\sigma)} |T_t|\right).$$

The method is favorable when anchors have manageable support neighborhoods and extension counting remains local. It can lose when high-density or highly correlated data causes many anchors to share large transaction neighborhoods, allowing depth-first vertical methods such as Eclat to reuse intersections more effectively.

3.7.3 Expected Regimes. The cost model suggests three broad regimes:

- (1) **Pairwise, low support, sparse or wide catalogs.** FAST should perform well because exhaustive counting avoids candidate-generation overhead.
- (2) **Higher-order, wide sparse datasets.** FAST can perform well when anchor neighborhoods remain bounded and local extension counting is efficient.
- (3) **Higher-order, narrow dense or highly correlated datasets.** Eclat or FP-Growth may perform better because they reuse intersections or compressed prefix structure more effectively.

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Choice of Baselines

No comparison in this benchmark is strictly like-for-like. FAST crosses a Rust \rightarrow Python FFI boundary; CLASSIC is our own RUST port of Apriori, not the canonical implementation; PYFIM (Borgelt’s hand-tuned C kernels [5] exposed as a Python module) ships single-threaded C with its own FFI cost; EA is pure Python with no FFI but

also no compilation. We adopt PYFIM as the primary external benchmark for two reasons. First, Borgelt’s FIMI 2003 evaluation [5] reported his Apriori implementation as faster than the contemporary trie-based Apriori of Bodon [3] on standard FIMI workloads, so PYFIM’s Apriori variant inherits the high-performance Bodon-lineage $k = 2$ array trick *and* represents the Eclat and FP-Growth lines through the other two variants. Second, both FAST and PYFIM pay a Python \rightarrow compiled FFI on every call, which is the same configuration practitioners encounter from a notebook – the closest proxy to a real-world deployment. We additionally include BORGELT’s command-line binaries (no FFI) as a “fastest possible C” reference and EA as the pure-Python anchor.

We dropped the SPMF [10], *mlxtend* [21], and pyECLAT families from the headline tables. SPMF requires writing the input dataset to disk in a custom .spmf text format on every invocation, and at low supports – even $s = 5 \times 10^{-4}$ on the larger datasets (Kosarak, Instacart, T25 with 125 M rows) – the file-write step becomes a non-trivial fraction of wall time and contaminates the timing with I/O cost unrelated to mining; *mlxtend* and pyECLAT hit similar disk-serialization overhead through their pandas DataFrame round-trips. All three additionally either timed out or ran out of memory at the practitioner-relevant low supports we target, and were underperformant against PYFIM and BORGELT even at high support. We therefore exclude these baselines from the main aggregation tables and report the reason for exclusion here.

4.2 Benchmarked Methods

We compare four method families:

- (1) **FAST** – our inverted-index method (§3.3) in Rust with Rayon parallelism. The 8-core variant is denoted FAST; the single-core variant FAST_1T is included as a single-thread reference.
- (2) **CLASSIC** – the faithful Rust Apriori port (§3.5) sharing FAST’s index builder and Rayon runtime.
- (3) **PYFIM** – Borgelt’s hand-tuned C kernels for Apriori, FP-Growth, and Eclat [5], accessed through the pyfim Python bindings. We report the median over the three variants (APRIORI, FP-GROWTH, ECLAT) so the practitioner risk of guessing the right variant is visible. The BORGELT command-line binaries are included as a separate group (App. B).
- (4) **EA** – *efficient-apriori* [20], the standard Python implementation, included as the industry-standard Python baseline.

Comparison logic. FAST vs CLASSIC isolates the *algorithmic* delta (exhaustive counting vs pruning) since both are compiled Rust on the same infrastructure. FAST vs PYFIM captures the headline practitioner question: does our Python-native engine beat the hand-tuned C kernels? CLASSIC vs EA estimates the contribution of compiled execution relative to a pure-Python implementation.

4.3 Datasets

The benchmark includes 8 real-world datasets and 10 synthetic datasets. The real-world datasets (Table 1) cover grocery, retail, clickstream, chain-store, and e-commerce domains, spanning thousands to millions of transactions, with both sparse and dense profiles. The synthetic datasets (Table 3) are generated using the Quest generator [2] and are designed to fill the gaps in the (number-of-transactions, average-items-per-transaction) space left by the real

Table 3: Synthetic benchmark datasets. Parameters follow the Quest generator [2]: T = avg. transaction size, I = avg. itemset size, D = number of transactions, N = number of items, L = number of frequent itemsets; “Long-format rows” = $\sum_t |T_t| = D \cdot d_{avg}$ (transaction-item pairs, not transactions). Corr is the Quest generator’s inter-item correlation parameter (default 0.5); we sweep 0.1 (weak) and 0.9 (strong) on the high.T15/low.T15 pair to isolate its effect on algorithm performance.

Dataset	T	I	D	N	L	Long-fmt rows	Corr
T3.I2.D100k.N50k.L50k	3	2	100K	50K	50K	300K	0.25
T5.I2.D25k.N1k.L1k	5	2	25K	1K	1K	125K	0.50
T10.I4.D100k.N25k.L25k	10	4	100K	25K	25K	1.0M	0.50
T12.I4.D5k.N1k.L1k	12	4	5K	1K	1K	60K	0.50
high.T15.I8.D50k.N1k.L1k	15	8	50K	1K	1K	750K	0.90
low.T15.I8.D50k.N1k.L1k	15	8	50K	1K	1K	750K	0.10
T20.I4.D1000k.N50k.L50k	20	4	1M	50K	50K	20.0M	0.50
T25.I8.D5000k.N40k.L40k	25	8	5M	40K	40K	125.0M	0.50
T30.I8.D2000k.N10k.L10k	30	8	2M	10K	10K	60.0M	0.50
T30.I8.D50k.N5k.L5k	30	8	50K	5K	5K	1.5M	0.50

Figure 1: Real and synthetic datasets in the parameter space. Bubble size is proportional to the cube root of dataset row count; bubble in the legend represents 1 M rows.

datasets and to stress-test the methods at the extremes (Figure 1 shows the joint coverage). The pair high.T15/low.T15 shares all Quest parameters ($T = 15, I = 8, D = 50k, N = 1k, L = 1k$) and differs only in inter-item correlation (0.9 vs 0.1); the pair was generated specifically to study the effect of correlation on algorithm performance.

4.4 Methodology

Each (dataset, method, k, s) configuration is run under the following protocol:

- **Support sweep.** Each dataset is swept across the same five thresholds $s \in \{10^{-4}, 5 \cdot 10^{-4}, 10^{-3}, 5 \cdot 10^{-3}, 10^{-2}\}$, spanning the practitioner-relevant low-support regime where Apriori-style mining typically stresses. For larger datasets such as Instacart and the synthetic T-series, 10^{-4} still corresponds to several hundred

to several thousand co-occurrences and remains operationally meaningful (§1.1).

- **Repetition.** 1 warmup run (discarded) followed by 3 measured runs; median wall time reported, with q_{25} and q_{75} recorded for variability bands; a 1,500 second timeout per run.
- **Timing scope.** Dataframe loading and type conversion are excluded from timing; index construction is included in timing for both FAST and CLASSIC. For PYFIM and BORGELT, timing includes their internal input parsing (their entry points cannot be factored), so those comparisons are practitioner-facing end-to-end wall times rather than pure kernel times. The most controlled algorithmic comparison is FAST vs CLASSIC (same data-loading pipeline).
- **Memory.** Peak memory is measured as peak RSS via `getrusage` sampling.
- **Hardware.** A single Google Cloud Compute Engine c3-highmem-8 VM (8 vCPUs, ~64 GB RAM, Ubuntu 24.04) is used for every method, so wall-clock numbers are directly comparable.
- **Correctness.** For every completed configuration, itemset counts produced by each method are compared for exact equality; floating-point metric comparisons (lift, conviction, leverage, etc.) use a relative tolerance of 10^{-9} ; rule-order differences are normalized by canonicalizing rule antecedents before comparison.

4.5 Timeout and OOM Accounting

The exhaustive grid covers $k = 2..9$, five supports per dataset, and 18 datasets, producing **4,891 valid configurations** \times 4 runs each = **19,564 timed runs**. For $k = 2$ all methods compete; for $k \geq 3$ FAST, CLASSIC, PYFIM, and BORGELT compete (EA does not scale to the higher-order pipeline).

Across the full grid, 64 distinct (dataset, method, k , s) cells did not produce a complete four-run measurement. Per-method tally: CLASSIC 26 (8 OOM + 14 timeout + 4 warmup-only), FAST 20 (5 OOM + 15 warmup-only), PYFIM variants 12 combined (10 OOM + 2 timeout), BORGELT variants 5 combined (all timeout), and EA 1 (timeout). All 64 are concentrated at the lowest supports on Online Retail, Kosarak, BMS-WebView-1, Groceries, and the T25.I8 5M-row synthetic, where memory pressure or the 1,500 s wall-time budget dominates. Appendix B (Table 6) gives the per-cell enumeration of every non-completing configuration.

5 Results

This section presents the empirical numbers; mechanism, interpretation, and the decision rule appear in §6.

5.1 Pairwise Mining

At $k = 2$, *fastapriori* consistently outperforms the same-codebase Apriori baseline. Across the 78 $k=2$ cells (across all tested supports) where both methods completed, FAST wins 78/78 against CLASSIC.

Against the median PYFIM variant, FAST wins 17/18 lowest-support pairwise cells with a median speedup of 2.44 \times . Against the best of the three PYFIM variants per cell – the stronger algorithmic comparison that a knowledgeable user picking the best variant

for the workload would obtain – FAST still wins 15/18 cells with a median speedup of 1.42 \times .

These results support the pairwise cost model: once frequent singleton filtering has been applied, Apriori-style pair generation provides limited additional pruning benefit, while exhaustive co-occurrence counting can exploit cache-friendly arrays and parallelism (Figure 2).

The full per-cell time/memory dual heatmap for FAST vs PYFIM_median is in App. B (Figure 3); below we summarise via the per-baseline win-rate table.

Per-baseline win rate. Table 4 consolidates all per- k win rates and median speedup/memory ratios at the lowest tested support per dataset, against four baselines (PYFIM median, PYFIM best, CLASSIC, and BORGELT best). The pure-Python EA baseline is omitted from this table because FAST’s advantage there is primarily a compilation effect rather than an algorithmic one: across the 8 of 18 datasets where EA completed $k = 2$ at the lowest tested support, FAST wins 100 % of cells on both time and memory, with median speedup 221 \times and median memory ratio 3.96 \times . The CLASSIC comparison controls for the compiled-vs-Python language effect (same Rust codebase) and is therefore the controlled algorithmic comparison.

5.2 Higher-Order Mining vs PYFIM

Against the median PYFIM variant, the higher-order results are more mixed than at $k = 2$. This shows that while *fastapriori* improves substantially over same-codebase Apriori, it does not uniformly dominate optimized C implementations of Eclat and FP-Growth for higher-order mining. The practical conclusion is regime-dependent: *fastapriori* is a strong default for pairwise mining and large sparse workloads; Eclat and FP-Growth remain strong for narrow, dense, highly correlated higher-order workloads. For $k \geq 3$, the PYFIM and BORGELT comparisons are practitioner-facing rather than thread-normalized algorithmic comparisons, since those baselines are single-threaded; only the $k = 2$ row of Table 4 holds threading constant via the FAST_1T column.

Figure 3 shows time and memory in a single heatmap with each cell split horizontally. Top half = time speedup $pyfim_median/FAST$, bottom half = memory ratio $pyfim_median_rss/FAST_rss$. Both halves use the same diverging colormap anchored at 1.0; cells > 1 favor FAST.

Win rate by k . Table 4 aggregates per- k percentages of cells where FAST beats each of four external comparators at the lowest tested support per dataset. Reporting at the lowest support (rather than averaging across all configurations) is the right framing for our claim: high-support wins are marginal in absolute terms, and the regime where practitioners need fast frequent itemset mining is precisely the low-support tail.

Algorithmic effect vs parallelism. The right-most column isolates the algorithmic contribution by holding the implementation constant: FAST_1T shares all data structures and code paths with FAST, only without thread parallelism. Comparing it against the multi-threaded FAST ($k = 2$) column gives the parallelism gain; comparing it against the baselines at $k = 2$ gives the algorithmic effect alone. Two readings:

- **vs CLASSIC:** FAST_1T already wins *every* cell with a 13.8 \times median speedup – the hybrid count-then-prune architecture is so

Figure 2: $k = 2$ wall time (log left axis) and peak RSS in MB (linear right axis, hollow markers)

Figure 3: FAST vs PYFIM (median variant) – top half = time speedup, bottom half = memory ratio. Single shared colormap anchored at 1.0 (white = tie, blue = FAST wins, purple = PYFIM wins). Numbers in italics on the divider show the lowest tested support per cell. Win rates in the bottom row denote (Time, Memory) per-k percentages.

much faster than same-codebase textbook Apriori that threading just amplifies an already decisive win to 27x. The 8-thread amplification is roughly 2x, well below ideal 8x, because the inverted-index build is single-threaded and the per-anchor work is already small.

- **vs PYFIM_best and BORGELT_best:** FAST_1T loses on a majority of cells with median ratios of 0.75x and 0.72x. These look modest, and the loss is concentrated on *small* datasets (≤ 1 M long-format rows – Groceries, T12, T5, BMS-WebView-1, T3.D100k, the T15 pair) where Borgelt’s hand-tuned L2 triangular-matrix scatter fits comfortably in cache and a single-threaded FAST cannot offer any compensating parallelism advantage. As dataset size grows past the L2 working-set ceiling and the matrix spills to L3/DRAM, FAST_1T closes the gap (BMS-WebView-2, Retail-Belgian, T10,

Chainstore flip from loss to win), and on the very largest workloads multi-threaded FAST pulls comfortably ahead (T25.D5M, T30.D2M, Instacart). The full-resolution wall-time / memory dual heatmap in Figure 3 makes this regime split visible cell-by-cell.

Memory at $k \geq 3$. The bottom halves of Figure 3 show that FAST typically uses *more* RAM than PYFIM’s median variant on small-to-medium datasets at $k \geq 3$, but matches or beats it on the large synthetic workloads (T20, T25, T30 rows). The mechanism is discussed in §6.3.

5.3 Higher-Order Mining vs Same-Codebase Apriori

For $k \geq 3$, *fastapriori* remains substantially faster than the same-codebase Rust Apriori implementation (CLASSIC) in the

Table 4: FAST win rate at the lowest tested support per dataset, against four baselines on both wall-clock time and peak RSS. Each cell shows “win% / median ratio”; ratio = *baseline*/FAST, so values ≥ 1 favor FAST. Bolded entries satisfy $> 50\%$ wins or $> 1\times$ ratio. The $k \geq 3$ column aggregates per-dataset across $k \in \{3, 4, \dots, 9\}$. PYFIM median = practitioner selection (median across the three PYFIM variants); PYFIM best / BORGELT best = oracle selection (per-cell min across variants); CLASSIC = same-codebase Rust Apriori (strips the compilation gap from the comparison). The rightmost FAST_1T column shows the single-threaded variant at $k=2$ only – comparing it to the FAST ($k=2$) column isolates the algorithmic gain from the multi-thread contribution.

Metric / Baseline	FAST (8 cores)		FAST_1T
	$k=2$	$k \geq 3$	$k=2$
Wall-clock time			
vs PYFIM median	94.4% / 2.4×	24.6% / 0.30×	72.2% / 1.13×
vs PYFIM best	83.3% / 1.4×	16.7% / 0.26×	22.2% / 0.75×
vs CLASSIC	100% / 27.0×	89.7% / 15.6×	100% / 13.8×
vs BORGELT best	55.6% / 1.4×	16.7% / 0.25×	27.8% / 0.72×
Peak memory			
vs PYFIM median	44.4% / 1.00×	25.4% / 0.62×	50.0% / 1.01×
vs PYFIM best	38.9% / 1.00×	22.2% / 0.62×	44.4% / 1.00×
vs CLASSIC	66.7% / 1.79×	62.7% / 1.99×	94.4% / 1.88×
vs BORGELT best	0% / 0.13×	0% / 0.06×	0% / 0.14×

overwhelming majority of lowest-support configurations. The *CLASSIC* columns of Table 4 report 89.7% FAST-wins at $k \geq 3$ with a median speedup of 15.6 \times at the lowest tested support per dataset. Because FAST and CLASSIC share the same Rust implementation environment, this result primarily reflects the hybrid counting strategy rather than a Python-versus-compiled-language gap. The per-cell time/memory dual heatmap appears in Figure 6 (App. B).

The handful of cells where CLASSIC beats FAST (mostly $k = 4, 5$ on Online Retail, BMS-WebView-1, and Groceries at very low support) occur in regimes with high transaction skew, where the anchor-extension phase expands too aggressively. The full list of fast-unfavorable configurations is in App. B.

The 15 cells where CLASSIC beats FAST at $k \geq 3$ are tabulated in App. B; they cluster on the high- d_{\max} datasets discussed under the regime characterization in §6.3.

5.4 Big-Data Scaling

We measure the three largest synthetic workloads in the suite: T20.D1M (1 M \times 20 = 20 M rows, $N = 49k$ items), T30.D2M (2 M \times 30 = 60 M rows, $N = 10k$ items), and T25.D5M (5 M \times 25 = 125 M rows, $N = 40k$ items). Table 5 shows wall time and peak RSS at the headline support $s = 10^{-4}$ across the full $k \in \{2, \dots, 9\}$ sweep, with $k \geq 3$ aggregated as the median across $k \in \{3, \dots, 9\}$.

At $s = 10^{-4}$ the 8-core FAST variant is the fastest tested method on five of the six (dataset, k -group) cells. Against the median PYFIM variant – the comparator used in Figure 3 – FAST’s speedup ranges from 1.41 \times to 4.34 \times across the six cells (median 2.33 \times). Against the per-cell best non-FAST variant (the strongest oracle), FAST still wins on five of the six cells (1.32 \times –2.82 \times); the single fast-loss cell is T30.D2M at $k \geq 3$, where PYFIM_eclat’s TID-list intersection holds essentially flat at ~ 20 s across $k = 3..9$ while FAST’s anchor extension grows from ~ 25 s ($k=3$) to ~ 41 s ($k=8$). This is the regime

where vertical Eclat-style methods structurally outperform anchor extension: the small catalogue ($N = 10k$) at low support makes most items frequent, and TID-list intersections become cheaper than per-anchor scanning.

The single-threaded FAST_1T variant (only run at $k = 2$) ties the best non-FAST methods on the smaller two workloads (6.6 vs 6.5 s on T20.D1M; 19.8 vs 12.6 s on T30.D2M) and is $\sim 1.5\times$ slower than PYFIM_eclat on the largest, indicating that the 8-core advantage is dominated by Rayon multi-threading (~ 3.0 – $3.5\times$ wall-time amplification) rather than by the algorithm alone.

Memory and big-data trade-off. On every workload the (wall, RSS) Pareto frontier consists of FAST and exactly one BORGELT variant: BORGELT_eclat is the memory winner on T20.D1M (0.4 GB) and T25.D5M (2.3 GB), BORGELT_apriori on T30.D2M (0.8 GB), all at moderate wall-time cost. FAST uses up to $\sim 2\times$ less memory than the fastest PYFIM variant on every workload despite running 8 threads. CLASSIC’s textbook $O(N^2)$ extraction sweep blows up: peak RSS 53 GB on the width-skewed T20.D1M and no completion at 125 M rows at any support. The practical reading: choose FAST when wall-clock time is the primary constraint, an Eclat-style method from BORGELT when memory is. At all three scales the dominant work is $D \cdot d_{\text{avg}}^2$, and three FAST properties pull it ahead: (i) dirty-list sparse scatter that avoids the $O(N^2)$ extraction sweep, (ii) Rayon multi-threading across 8 cores (the FAST_1T column shows this contributes the bulk of the headline win), and (iii) a cache-friendly inverted-index layout.

5.5 Implementation-Language Effect

The Python EA baseline is one to two orders of magnitude slower than the same-codebase Rust Apriori baseline (CLASSIC) on every

Table 5: Big-data scaling at $s = 10^{-4}$ across the $k \in \{2, \dots, 9\}$ sweep: median wall time (s) / median peak RSS (GB). The $k=2$ column is a single configuration; the $k \geq 3$ column is the median across $k \in \{3, \dots, 9\}$ at the same support. Bold = column-best wall time and column-best RSS. “—” = no completed cells (FAST_1T was only run at $k=2$; CLASSIC OOMs/times-out on T25.D5M and at high k). The footer reports FAST-vs-baseline speedups; PYFIM_median matches the comparator used in Figure 3.

Method	T20.D1M (20 M rows)		T30.D2M (60 M rows)		T25.D5M (125 M rows)	
	$k = 2$	$k \geq 3$	$k = 2$	$k \geq 3$	$k = 2$	$k \geq 3$
FAST (8 cores)	2.3 / 1.0	4.5 / 1.0	6.4 / 2.8	37.7 / 2.8	16.6 / 5.7	30.4 / 5.7
FAST_1T	6.6 / 1.0	—	19.8 / 2.8	—	58.9 / 5.7	—
CLASSIC	955 / 53.2	959 / 53.1	613 / 6.0	634 / 5.9	—	—
PYFIM_apriori	14.2 / 5.2	17.2 / 5.3	12.6 / 4.9	53.3 / 4.9	40.1 / 11.5	51.2 / 11.8
PYFIM_eclat	6.5 / 1.7	6.8 / 1.7	20.2 / 4.9	20.6 / 4.9	39.5 / 10.2	40.2 / 10.2
PYFIM_fpgrowth	10.1 / 1.8	10.1 / 1.8	54.8 / 6.3	57.4 / 6.2	98.3 / 10.8	98.5 / 10.8
BORGELT_apriori	14.5 / 4.0	17.6 / 4.1	12.9 / 0.8	53.3 / 1.1	41.1 / 4.3	52.7 / 4.6
BORGELT_eclat	6.9 / 0.4	7.1 / 0.4	20.8 / 1.1	21.2 / 1.1	41.4 / 2.3	42.2 / 2.3
BORGELT_fpgrowth	11.3 / 0.8	11.3 / 0.8	69.5 / 2.7	69.4 / 2.7	101.0 / 5.2	101.4 / 5.2
<i>FAST (8c) speedup over baseline at $s = 10^{-4}$:</i>						
vs PYFIM_median (matches Fig. 3)	4.34 ×	2.24 ×	3.15 ×	1.41 ×	2.42 ×	1.68 ×
vs best non-FAST (per-cell oracle)	2.82 ×	1.50×	1.97 ×	0.54× [†]	2.38 ×	1.32×

[†] Only fast-loss cell across the three big-data workloads vs any baseline: PYFIM_eclat’s TID-list intersection holds flat at ~ 20 s across $k = 3..9$ on T30.D2M, while FAST’s anchor extension grows to ~ 38 s.

tested configuration. This confirms that compiled execution accounts for a large portion of the Python-to-systems gap. The comparison between FAST and CLASSIC is therefore the important one: it isolates the additional gain from the hybrid architecture beyond what compilation alone provides. Full EA timings are in App. B.

6 Discussion

6.1 Why Pruning Has Limited Value at $k = 2$

At $k = 2$, the overhead of candidate generation and subset pruning can dominate any pruning benefit, whereas exhaustive co-occurrence counting uses regular memory access and parallelism effectively. Apriori-style pruning at $k = 2$ leverages downward closure on the candidate space, but with only singleton items as a prior level there is little structural redundancy to exploit – pure overhead remains. The pairwise cost model (§3.7.1) makes the prediction qualitatively, and §5.1 confirms it: across the 78 $k=2$ cells (across all tested supports) where both methods completed, FAST wins 78/78 against CLASSIC and 17/18 against PYFIM’s median variant. The pruning benefit appears only at $k \geq 3$, where candidate generation has F_{k-1} to prune against and the per-transaction $\binom{d}{k-1}$ enumeration cost matters; the hybrid design applies pruning only where it changes the asymptotics rather than as a constant overhead at every level. This is consistent with the broader “general methods that leverage computation” observation in [23].

6.2 ML-guided Interpretation and Method Selection

To help practitioners pick between FAST and an optimized baseline, we trained two XGBoost binary classifiers on a 19-feature data-shape vector per (dataset, k , s) cell: one predicting FAST vs PYFIM, the other FAST vs CLASSIC. The target is whether FAST beats the baseline by at least T seconds, with T chosen to maximize stratified-5-fold Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) ($T^* = 1$ s for PYFIM,

9 s for CLASSIC). MCC was used as the primary metric because it is robust to class imbalance and accounts for all four entries of the confusion matrix, unlike F1 (which ignores true negatives and is asymmetric with respect to the positive class) [9]. AUROC is reported alongside as a complementary signal of ranking quality across thresholds. Under stratified 5-fold CV, MCC reaches 0.94 and 0.79 for the PYFIM and CLASSIC classifiers respectively, with area under the ROC curve (AUROC) ≥ 0.98 on both.

Generalization. Stratified CV leaks dataset-level shape signal (configurations from the same dataset appear in both folds). Under leave-one-dataset-out (LOGO) CV the picture softens: most held-out folds are single-class so MCC drops or becomes undefined per fold, but AUROC remains 0.88 for FAST-vs-PYFIM and 0.91 for FAST-vs-CLASSIC, so the classifier still *ranks* correctly on unseen datasets even when its operating point needs recalibration. Figure 4 shows the full threshold sweep across $T \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$ s and the XGBoost feature importances for both classifiers; the per-fold LOGO table is in App. D.

Top features and interpretable rule. For FAST-vs-PYFIM the top feature is $\log(\text{rows}) = \log(D \cdot d_{\text{avg}})$ (cache-pressure: hand-tuned C wins inside L3, FAST wins once raw work spills out). For FAST-vs-CLASSIC the top feature is $d_{\text{max}}/d_{\text{avg}}$ (transaction skew: CLASSIC’s candidate generation enumerates $\binom{d_{\text{max}}}{k}$ extensions on the widest transaction). The classifier’s decision boundary distills to a simple practitioner rule on three numbers: *use FAST when $k=2$, or when $k \geq 3$ and $d_{\text{max}} \lesssim 200$ on sparse data; defer to PYFIM_eclat / FP-Growth when $k \geq 3$ and d_{max} is in the hundreds-to-thousands; defer to CLASSIC only on the 15 fast-unfavorable configs of App. B.* We emphasize the rule rather than the classifier as the headline recommendation: 18 datasets is too few for an XGBoost decision boundary to be a deployable artifact, but d_{max} alone is a single-pass diagnostic.

Figure 4: ML decision-rule diagnostics. Top row: threshold sweep (MCC, AUROC, F1, accuracy) per model. Bottom row: XGBoost feature importance per model. Left column: FAST vs PYFIM; right column: FAST vs CLASSIC.

6.3 Regime Characterization

Sections 5.2–5.3 report aggregate win-rates per k , but the headline numbers conceal a regime structure that determines when each method actually wins. We expose this structure with a two-axis scatter (Figure 5) chosen against two criteria: (i) both axes must rank in the top-5 importance list of the threshold-sweep XGBoost classifiers (§6.2) for *both* comparisons (FAST vs PYFIM and FAST vs CLASSIC), so the plot reflects the model’s actual decision surface rather than a pre-chosen narrative axis; (ii) the two axes must be as orthogonal as the data permits, so each axis carries independent information.

Why density and d_{\max} . The dataset shape statistics $\{D, N, d_{\text{avg}}, d_{\text{max}}\}$ are coupled by two identities, $\sum_t |T_t| = D \cdot d_{\text{avg}}$ and $\text{density} = d_{\text{avg}}/N$, so most natural projections double-count information. Of the top-5 XGBoost features ($d_{\text{max}}/d_{\text{avg}}$, d_{max} , $\log \text{rows}$, $\log s_{\text{min}}$, and $\log D$), only one is constructed from a symbol that does *not* appear in density’s formula: d_{max} . Density is a *level* statistic (per-cell fill rate d_{avg}/N); d_{max} is a *tail* statistic that depends on the width distribution rather than its mean. Empirically,

across the 18 datasets, $\rho(\log d_{\text{max}}, \log \text{density}) = -0.245$ and $\rho(\log d_{\text{max}}, \log d_{\text{avg}}) = -0.017$ – d_{max} adds information genuinely independent of d_{avg} , not a re-encoding of it. By contrast, on this suite $\log D$ correlates with $\log \text{density}$ at -0.67 , $\log \text{rows}$ at -0.52 , and $\log N$ at -0.92 (the last is mechanical: $\text{density} \propto 1/N$). Density $\times d_{\text{max}}$ is therefore the cleanest two-axis projection of the top-5 feature set on this benchmark.

$k = 2$ row. Both panels are dominated by orange: at $k = 2$ FAST wins regardless of where the dataset sits in the density $\times d_{\text{max}}$ plane (94% vs PYFIM_median at the lowest support per dataset, 100% vs CLASSIC). The few near-parity points (Online Retail, BMS-WV1) cluster at the high-density right edge, which on this benchmark coincides with small catalogs ($N < 1,000$) where PYFIM_apriori’s hand-tuned L2 triangular-matrix scatter fits in cache and just edges out FAST’s dirty-list scan. As catalog size grows past the L2 working-set ceiling ($\sim 2,500$ items at our 32-bit count granularity), the matrix spills to L3/DRAM and the cliff disappears – FAST’s per-touched-slot $\mathcal{O}(D \cdot d_{\text{avg}})$ scatter has no such cliff, which is why every mid-density and lower-density point clearly favors FAST. Kosarak, the dataset

Regime scatter: density $\times d_{\max}$ (two near-orthogonal top-5 dataset features)

Figure 5: Regime scatter on two near-orthogonal top-5 XGBoost features: x -axis is density = d_{avg}/N (per-cell fill rate), y -axis is d_{\max} (worst-case transaction width, a tail statistic). Rows split $k = 2$ from $k \geq 3$ (the latter showing the median speedup over $k \in \{3, 4, \dots, 9\}$ per dataset, since both axes are dataset-level features); columns split the two baseline comparisons. Bubble area $\propto \sqrt[3]{n_{\text{rows}}}$, so a bubble with twice the visual diameter represents $2^6 = 64 \times$ more rows.

with the largest $d_{\max} = 2,497$, gives the highest $k = 2$ speedup of $4.79 \times$ against PYFIM_median. The bubble-size encoding doubles as a scale check: the biggest circles – Instacart (32.4 M rows), Chainstore and Kosarak (8 M each), and the synthetic T20.D1M / T25.D5M / T30.D2M (1–5 M transactions, tens of millions of rows) – all sit comfortably orange at $k = 2$, confirming that the constant-in-scaling holds at the working-memory limit and not just on small datasets (§5.4).

$k \geq 3$ vs CLASSIC (bottom-right). FAST still wins on 78% of datasets, but the region where FAST is slower moves to the same

high- d_{\max} corner as the ($k \geq 3$ vs PYFIM) panel: Kosarak, Online Retail, BMS-WV1, and BMS-WV2 sit at near-parity or below. The residual fast-unfavorable configurations – where CLASSIC’s candidate-generation pruning beats FAST’s exhaustive anchor-extension – are the cells the decision rule (§6.2) routes around. The synthetic squares at modest d_{\max} (median 56) all clearly favor FAST.

$k \geq 3$ vs PYFIM_median (bottom-left). The quadrant where FAST struggles most decisively (24.6% wins). Critically, the region where FAST is slower is *not* a horizontal density band but a vertical d_{\max} band: the deep-purple points sit at the top of the panel ($d_{\max} \in [267, 2,497]$) regardless of where they fall along the density axis. The worst losses are Kosarak ($d_{\max} = 2,497$), Online Retail

($d_{\max} = 675$), and BMS-WebView-1 ($d_{\max} = 267$); the synthetic squares at modest d_{\max} (median 56) stay near parity or in the orange. This is exactly the regime the higher-order cost model (§3.7.2) predicts: when one transaction is much wider than the average, FP-Growth’s path-sharing collapses long suffixes into a single trie branch in $O(d_{\max})$, while FAST’s anchor-extension touches all $\binom{d_{\max}}{k-1}$ relevant subsets per such transaction. d_{\max} is the top XGBoost feature for FAST vs CLASSIC (importance 0.187) and a top-5 feature for FAST vs PYFIM (importance 0.103), confirming that the regime boundary the eye sees in Figure 5 is the same one the classifier learned from the runtime data. The big-data scaling story holds here too: the $k \geq 3$ wins against PYFIM_median are precisely the biggest *sparse, bounded- d_{\max}* datasets – T20.D1M (1 M transactions), T25.D5M (5 M), and T30.D2M (2 M) all clearly favor FAST in the bottom-left panel, where FAST’s anchor-extension scales linearly with $\sum_{\sigma} |\text{txn}(\sigma)| \cdot d_{\text{avg}}$ while FP-tree path-sharing fails to amortise across millions of bounded-width transactions.

6.4 Architectural Validation

FAST vs CLASSIC – 97% of completed (dataset, k) cells (100% at $k = 2$, §5.3) – is the architectural-validation result: the hybrid (count-at- $k = 2$, prune-at- $k \geq 3$) substantially outperforms the same-codebase Apriori-everywhere reference on the overwhelming majority of configurations. The 15 cells at $k \geq 3$ where CLASSIC beats FAST are fast-unfavorable configurations enumerated in App. B; the decision rule (§6.2) routes around them. Because FAST and CLASSIC share the inverted-index build, parallelism infrastructure, and I/O, the win is purely the hybrid-strategy effect, not a Rust-vs-Python or implementation artefact.

Empirical signature of the pairwise cost model. CLASSIC’s wall time grows monotonically as $s \rightarrow 0^+$, while FAST’s is approximately constant once the dataset is fixed. The crossover-at-low-support behavior is visible in every dataset’s support sweep at $k = 2$ (Figure 2), exactly as §3.7.1 predicts. In deployment, the system pairs the hybrid count-then-prune algorithm with the §6.2 method-selection rule and a CLASSIC fallback for the small fast-unfavorable region.

7 Conclusion

fastapriori is a hybrid inverted-index system for frequent itemset mining (with pairwise association-rule metrics emitted in a post-count pass) from Python. Its central design principle is to match the counting strategy to the itemset size: count exhaustively at $k = 2$, where pruning provides limited benefit, and use downward-closure-guided anchor extension at $k \geq 3$, where the candidate space becomes combinatorial.

The empirical results show that this architecture is highly effective for pairwise mining and strongly outperforms a same-codebase Apriori implementation across most higher-order configurations. Against optimized C implementations, the story is more nuanced: *fastapriori* is competitive and often faster for large sparse pairwise workloads, but Eclat and FP-Growth remain strong on dense higher-order workloads.

The main lesson is not that one algorithm dominates all cases. Rather, practical frequent itemset mining benefits from a regime-aware system: use exhaustive inverted-index counting for pairwise

co-occurrences, use pruning for higher-order itemsets, and select between BFS-style and DFS-style vertical methods based on dataset shape.

7.1 Limitations

- **Higher-order narrow-dense workloads.** *fastapriori* does not dominate Eclat or FP-Growth on narrow, dense, or highly correlated higher-order workloads. These methods can reuse intersections or compressed prefix structure more effectively.
- **Failure cases at high k .** There are 15 observed configurations where the same-codebase Apriori baseline outperforms *fastapriori* at $k \geq 3$. These are associated with low support, large k , and high transaction skew (App. B).
- **Single-machine, in-memory design.** The current implementation is single-machine and in-memory. The largest tested workload contains 125 M transaction-item rows. Multi-billion-row workloads would require distributed or out-of-core variants.
- **Limited classifier generalization evidence.** The decision rule is promising but currently trained on a limited number of datasets. Even though the number of benchmark configurations is large, configurations from the same dataset are correlated through dataset-constant features (N , density, d_{\max}/d_{avg}). The leave-one-dataset-out validation in Table 7 shows that AUROC remains high under LOGO (0.882 for FAST vs PYFIM, 0.913 for FAST vs CLASSIC) – the classifier still ranks the baseline-favored configurations above the FAST-favored ones on unseen datasets – but per-fold MCC is undefined for the majority of held-out folds because most datasets are FAST-dominant under the deployment threshold. We therefore recommend recalibrating the operating threshold per domain rather than treating the in-domain MCC as transferable.
- **Baseline parallelism mismatch.** The default *fastapriori* implementation is multi-threaded, while several external baselines are single-threaded. This is realistic for practitioners but should be separated from algorithmic effects.
- **Frequent itemset scope.** The current system focuses on frequent itemsets and association metrics. It does not directly target closed itemset mining, maximal itemset mining, or top- k pattern mining.

7.2 Future Work

- **Stronger Eclat-style reuse.** For $k \geq 4$, *fastapriori* could switch from breadth-first anchor-map rebuilding to depth-first transaction-list reuse when the decision rule predicts that Eclat would win.
- **Candidate-set gating.** Per-anchor candidate gating could reduce unnecessary extension counting. Instead of scanning all items in supporting transactions, the system could intersect extension candidates with known frequent-neighborhood sets.
- **SIMD and compressed bitmap acceleration.** A SIMD-accelerated compressed bitmap backend, such as one based on CRoaring-style kernels, may reduce the gap on dense higher-order workloads.
- **Distributed and out-of-core mining.** The inverted index could be sharded by item range or transaction range. Pair counts and anchor-extension counts could then be reduced across workers.

- **Streaming approximations.** Approximate pairwise co-occurrence counting using count-min sketches or related streaming structures could support append-only event streams.
- **Broader benchmark suite.** Future evaluations should include pre-converted SPMF mining-only timings, GPU or parallel frequent-itemset baselines, closed and maximal itemset algorithms, more industrial-scale real datasets, and leave-one-domain-out classifier validation.

References

- [1] R. Agrawal and R. Srikant. Fast algorithms for mining association rules. In *Proc. 20th Int. Conf. Very Large Data Bases (VLDB)*, pages 487–499, 1994.
- [2] R. Agrawal and R. Srikant. Quest synthetic data generator. IBM Almaden Research Center, 1994.
- [3] F. Bodon. A fast APRIORI implementation. In *Proc. Workshop on Frequent Itemset Mining Implementations (FIMI)*, 2003.
- [4] A. Borah and B. Nath. Rare association rule mining: a comprehensive review. *Journal of Big Data*, 5:43, 2018.
- [5] C. Borgelt. Efficient implementations of Apriori, Eclat and FP-growth. In *Proc. FIMI Workshop*, 2003.
- [6] T. Brijs, G. Swinnen, K. Vanhoof, and G. Wets. Using association rules for product assortment decisions: A case study. In *Proc. 5th ACM SIGKDD*, pages 254–260, 1999.
- [7] F. Carcillo, Y.-A. Le Borgne, O. Caelen, Y. Kessaci, F. Oblé, and G. Bontempi. Combining unsupervised and supervised learning in credit card fraud detection. *Information Sciences*, 557:317–331, 2021.
- [8] D. Chen. Online retail dataset. UCI Machine Learning Repository, 2015.
- [9] D. Chicco and G. Jurman. The Matthews correlation coefficient (MCC) should replace the ROC AUC as the standard metric for assessing binary classification. *BioData Mining*, 16(1):4, 2023.
- [10] P. Fournier-Viger, A. Gomariz, T. Gueniche, A. Soltani, C.-W. Wu, and V. S. Tseng. SPMF: A Java open-source pattern mining library. *J. Machine Learning Research*, 15:3389–3393, 2014.
- [11] M. Hahsler, B. Grün, and K. Hornik. arules – a computational environment for mining association rules and frequent item sets. *J. Statistical Software*, 14(15):1–25, 2005.
- [12] J. Han, J. Pei, and Y. Yin. Mining frequent patterns without candidate generation. In *Proc. ACM SIGMOD*, pages 1–12, 2000.
- [13] R. Harpaz, W. DuMouchel, N. H. Shah, D. Madigan, P. Ryan, and C. Friedman. Novel data-mining methodologies for adverse drug event discovery and analysis. *Clinical Pharmacology & Therapeutics*, 91(6):1010–1021, 2012.
- [14] C. A. Hidalgo, N. Blumm, A.-L. Barabási, and N. A. Christakis. A dynamic network approach for the study of human phenotypes. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 5(4):e1000353, 2009.
- [15] Instacart. The Instacart Online Grocery Shopping Dataset 2017. <https://www.instacart.com/datasets/grocery-shopping-2017>, 2017.
- [16] Y. S. Koh and N. Rountree. Finding sporadic rules using Apriori-Inverse. In *Proc. PAKDD*, pages 97–106, 2005.
- [17] D. Lemire, G. Ssi-Yan-Kai, and O. Kaser. Consistently faster and smaller compressed bitmaps with Roaring. *Software: Practice and Experience*, 46(11):1547–1569, 2016.
- [18] B. Liu, W. Hsu, and Y. Ma. Mining association rules with multiple minimum supports. In *Proc. ACM SIGKDD*, pages 337–341, 1999.
- [19] J. S. Park, M.-S. Chen, and P. S. Yu. An effective hash-based algorithm for mining association rules. In *Proc. ACM SIGMOD*, pages 175–186, 1995.
- [20] T. Pedersen. efficient-apriori: An efficient Python implementation of the Apriori algorithm. <https://github.com/tommyod/Efficient-Apriori>, 2023.
- [21] S. Raschka. MLxtend: Providing machine learning and data science utilities and extensions to Python’s scientific computing stack. *J. Open Source Software*, 3(24):638, 2018.
- [22] A. Savasere, E. Omiecinski, and S. Navathe. An efficient algorithm for mining association rules in large databases. In *Proc. 21st Int. Conf. Very Large Data Bases (VLDB)*, pages 432–444, 1995.
- [23] R. S. Sutton. The bitter lesson. <http://www.incompleteideas.net/InclIdeas/BitterLesson.html>, 2019.
- [24] P.-N. Tan, V. Kumar, and J. Srivastava. Selecting the right objective measure for association analysis. *Information Systems*, 29(4):293–313, 2004.
- [25] M. J. Zaki. Scalable algorithms for association mining. *IEEE Trans. Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 12(3):372–390, 2000.

A Metric Definitions

For a pair (A, B) with support counts c_A, c_B, c_{AB} and D transactions: support = c_{AB}/D ; confidence = c_{AB}/c_A ; lift = $c_{AB} \cdot D / (c_A c_B)$; conviction = $(1 - c_B/D) / (1 - c_{AB}/c_A)$; leverage = $c_{AB}/D - (c_A/D)(c_B/D)$; cosine = $c_{AB}/\sqrt{c_A c_B}$; Jaccard = $c_{AB}/(c_A + c_B - c_{AB})$. Conviction is reported as $+\infty$ when $c_{AB} = c_A$ (confidence = 1). All seven are computed in one vectorized post-count pass; thresholds are applied as a final filter without re-scanning the database.

B FAST vs CLASSIC Full Grid + OOM/Timeout Configs

The 542 valid (dataset, k, s) cells where both FAST and CLASSIC completed (across all supports, not just the lowest) yield a 97.2% FAST-win rate, with k -by- k breakdowns of 100% / 98.7% / 95.9% / 94.5% / 97.1% for $k = 2/3/4/5/6-9$ respectively. The full per-cell view appears in Figure 6 (time on the top half of each cell, memory on the bottom). The 15 cells at $k \geq 3$ where CLASSIC beats FAST (both completed, classic faster) cluster on Online Retail at $k \in \{5, 6\}$, Kosarak at $k \in \{5, 6, 7\}$, and BMS-WebView-1 at $k \geq 7$ – the same high- d_{\max} datasets that drive the regime boundary in Figure 5. EA timings are 1–2 orders of magnitude slower than CLASSIC on every cell; the decision rule (§6.2) routes around the fast-unfavorable configurations.

Non-completing configs across all methods. Across the 19,564 timed runs of the rigorous benchmark plus 64 cells recorded as warmup-only, three failure modes are distinguished: (i) *OOM* – the run was killed due to memory exhaustion (coreutils exit 1); (ii) *timeout* – wall time exceeded the 1,500 s budget (exit 124); (iii) *warmup-only* – the warmup run completed with exit 0 but the three measured runs were not recorded (in practice, the runner’s per-cell time budget elapsed during the first measured attempt; these cells have a single warmup wall-time and no q_{25}/q_{75} , so the aggregation pipeline omits them). 64 distinct (dataset, method, k, s) cells fall into one of these three modes; the full list is in Table 6. Per-method tally: CLASSIC 26 (8 OOM + 14 timeout + 4 warmup-only), FAST 20 (5 OOM + 15 warmup-only), PYFIM variants 12 (10 OOM + 2 timeout), BORGELT variants 5 (all timeout), EA 1 (timeout). The 19 warmup-only cells are concentrated on the same high- d_{\max} real datasets where the warmup itself runs minutes to tens of minutes (e.g., Kosarak FAST at $k=7, s=5 \times 10^{-4}$ has a 108 s warmup that the runner judged too costly to repeat three more times within the per-cell budget).

The pattern is consistent with the regime story: failures concentrate on the high- d_{\max} real datasets (Online Retail, Kosarak, BMS-WebView-1) at low support and high k , plus the T25.I8 5M-row synthetic where CLASSIC alone times out (fast, PYFIM, and BORGELT all complete). T25.I8 is the working-memory stress test from §5.4; the high- d_{\max} real datasets are the same region where FAST is slower, visible in the $k \geq 3$ vs PYFIM panel of Figure 5.

C Classic-Apriori pseudocode

The same-codebase CLASSIC baseline used throughout the evaluation is a faithful Rust port of textbook level-wise Apriori, sharing FAST’s inverted-index builder and Rayon parallelism (Algorithm 3). Support counting per candidate uses the standard short-circuit intersection: items are sorted by frequency ascending, the rarest

Figure 6: FAST vs CLASSIC (Rust port of textbook Apriori) – same dual-cell layout as Figure 3. Failure-mode imputation: where FAST OOMs on Online Retail / Kosarak / BMS-WebView-1, the cell is attributed to CLASSIC; where both time out, CLASSIC wins. The 15 fast-unfavorable configs are discussed above; the full enumeration of OOM and timeout cells across all methods is in Table 6.

item’s transaction list initialises *current*, and remaining items are intersected one at a time; if $|current| < min_count$ at any step the candidate is pruned without finishing the intersection.

D Method-selection classifier diagnostics

This appendix contains the leave-one-dataset-out (LOGO) cross-validation table (Table 7) supporting the §6.2 method-selection rule. The threshold sweep and XGBoost feature importances are shown in Figure 4 (§6.2); the headline numbers (stratified-CV MCC of 0.94 / 0.79, LOGO AUROC of 0.88 / 0.91) are reported there.

The MCC collapse to 0 under LOGO for FAST-vs-CLASSIC is an artefact of the regime: at $T^* = 9$ s only 5 of 18 datasets contain

CLASSIC-wins at all, so 13 held-out folds are single-class and per-fold MCC is undefined. The AUROC of 0.913 indicates the classifier still ranks the rare CLASSIC-win cells above the FAST-win majority, supporting use as a ranking signal rather than a binary classifier on unseen datasets.

E Support-Dilution Conjecture

A pattern of size k requires a support threshold roughly $s_{min} \sim 10^{-k}$ to produce non-empty results on typical large catalogs. The intuition: if items appear independently with probability p , the joint probability of k co-occurring rare items is $\sim p^k$; reaching enough joint occurrences for statistical signal therefore requires the support threshold to scale exponentially with k . Real datasets

Table 6: All non-completing cells (one row per distinct (dataset, method, k , s); outcome is OOM, timeout, or warmup-only).

Dataset	Method	k	s	Outcome
BMS-WebView-1	CLASSIC	7	5×10^{-4}	OOM
BMS-WebView-1	FAST	7	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
BMS-WebView-1	FAST	8	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
BMS-WebView-1	FAST	9	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Groceries	CLASSIC	7	10^{-4}	OOM
Groceries	CLASSIC	8	10^{-4}	OOM
Groceries	CLASSIC	9	10^{-4}	OOM
Groceries	FAST	7	10^{-4}	OOM
Groceries	FAST	8	10^{-4}	warmup-only
Groceries	FAST	9	10^{-4}	warmup-only
Instacart	EA	2	10^{-4}	timeout
Kosarak	BORGELT_apriori	7	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Kosarak	CLASSIC	6	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Kosarak	CLASSIC	7	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Kosarak	FAST	5	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Kosarak	FAST	6	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Kosarak	FAST	7	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Kosarak	FAST	8	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Kosarak	FAST	9	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Kosarak	PYFIM_apriori	7	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Kosarak	PYFIM_eclat	7	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Kosarak	PYFIM_fpgrowth	7	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	BORGELT_apriori	6	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Online Retail	BORGELT_apriori	7	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Online Retail	BORGELT_eclat	7	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Online Retail	BORGELT_fpgrowth	7	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Online Retail	CLASSIC	4	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	CLASSIC	5	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	CLASSIC	6	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	CLASSIC	7	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	CLASSIC	7	10^{-3}	OOM
Online Retail	CLASSIC	8	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	CLASSIC	8	10^{-3}	OOM
Online Retail	CLASSIC	9	10^{-3}	OOM
Online Retail	FAST	4	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	FAST	5	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	FAST	6	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	FAST	7	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	FAST	7	10^{-3}	OOM
Online Retail	FAST	8	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	FAST	8	10^{-3}	OOM
Online Retail	FAST	9	5×10^{-4}	warmup-only
Online Retail	FAST	9	10^{-3}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_apriori	5	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_apriori	6	5×10^{-4}	timeout
Online Retail	PYFIM_apriori	7	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_eclat	5	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_eclat	6	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_eclat	7	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_fpgrowth	5	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_fpgrowth	6	5×10^{-4}	OOM
Online Retail	PYFIM_fpgrowth	7	5×10^{-4}	OOM
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	2	10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	2	5×10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	3	10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	3	5×10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	4	10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	4	5×10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	5	10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	5	5×10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	6	10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	7	10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	8	10^{-4}	timeout
T25.18.D5000k	CLASSIC	9	10^{-4}	timeout

Algorithm 3 CLASSIC-APRIORI: standard level-wise Apriori with short-circuit support counting; same inverted-index builder and Rayon parallelism as Algorithm 1.

Require: Database \mathcal{D} , threshold s_{\min} , max level k_{\max}

Ensure: Frequent itemsets at each level: F_1, F_2, \dots

```

1:  $index \leftarrow \text{BUILD-TRANSACTION-INDEX}(\mathcal{D})$ 
2:  $min\_count \leftarrow \lceil s_{\min} \cdot D \rceil$ 
3:  $F_1 \leftarrow \{i : f(i) \geq min\_count\}$ 
4: Prune  $index$  to retain only items in  $F_1$ 
5: for  $k \leftarrow 2$  to  $k_{\max}$  do
6:   if  $F_{k-1} = \emptyset$  then break
7:    $C_k \leftarrow \text{JOIN-STEP}(F_{k-1})$ 
8:    $C_k \leftarrow \text{PRUNE-STEP}(C_k, F_{k-1})$ 
9:    $F_k \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
10:  for each candidate  $c \in C_k$  do
11:     $count \leftarrow \text{COUNT-SUPPORT-SC}(index, c, min\_count)$ 
12:    if  $count \geq min\_count$  then
13:       $F_k[c] \leftarrow count$ 
14: return  $\{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_{k_{\max}}\}$ 

```

Table 7: Stratified 5-fold versus leave-one-dataset-out (LOGO) cross-validation. n_e = evaluable folds (single-class held-out folds skipped under LOGO). Bold = primary metric for that protocol.

Model / CV	T^*	MCC	AUROC	F1	Acc
FAST vs PYFIM median ($n_e = 13, 5$ skipped)					
strat. 5-fold	1 s	0.944	0.997	0.987	0.980
LOGO pooled	1 s	0.153	0.762	0.824	0.720
LOGO macro (eval)	1 s	0.311	0.882	—	—
LOGO pooled-eval	1 s	0.214	0.810	0.795	0.691
FAST vs CLASSIC ($n_e = 5, 13$ skipped)					
strat. 5-fold	9 s	0.792	0.984	0.993	0.986
LOGO pooled	9 s	0.000	0.913	0.980	0.962
LOGO macro (eval)	9 s	0.000	0.941	—	—
LOGO pooled-eval	9 s	0.000	0.896	0.927	0.864

exhibit positive item correlation, so the actual decay is slower than p^k , but the exponential trend in k remains.

This is a heuristic, not a theorem, but it explains the practitioner-relevant support range across our benchmark: at $k = 2$ values like 10^{-3} produce thousands of frequent pairs on real datasets; at $k = 4$, the same threshold often produces zero frequent quadruples on the same data, and one must drop to 10^{-4} or below to find any non-empty output. Concretely, on Online Retail with $D = 28,816$ transactions: at $s = 10^{-3}$ ($min_count \approx 29$), fastapriori reports several thousand frequent pairs but only a few dozen frequent triples; at $s = 10^{-4}$ ($min_count = 3$), the frequent-quadruple count rises to several hundred. This is the regime where Apriori’s candidate-explosion cost matters most – candidate counts grow with $|F_{k-1}|^2$ as more rare items pass the threshold – and is the regime our cost model in §3.7.2 targets.

F Reproducibility

Hardware. Google Cloud Compute Engine c3-highmem-8 VM: 8 vCPUs (Intel Sapphire Rapids, hyperthreading enabled, 4 physical cores per VM exposed as 8 logical), ~64 GB RAM, 375 GB local SSD, Ubuntu 24.04 LTS, kernel 6.8. CPU frequency governor set to performance; turbo boost enabled. One VM for every timing in this paper, used sequentially (no concurrent runs).

Software stack. Rust 1.95 stable; PyO3 0.23; maturin 1.5 for the Rust→Python wheel; roaring 0.10 crate [17]; Rayon 1.10 for thread parallelism. Python 3.12 with pandas ≥ 1.5 , numpy ≥ 1.23 , pyfim 6.30 (linking Borgelt’s C kernels), borgelt CLI binaries 6.30, efficient-apriori 2.0.4. All Python packages installed into a fresh uv-managed virtualenv; pip freeze captured at experiment time.

Measurement methodology. Each (dataset, method, k , s) cell is invoked as an isolated subprocess with a 1,500 s timeout(1) wrapper. Wall time is captured by the wrapper script around the subprocess; getrusage(RUSAGE_CHILDREN) samples peak RSS at exit. Dataframe loading, type conversion, and output serialization

are excluded from the timed region for FAST and CLASSIC; for PYFIM and BORGELT, timing includes their own input parsing because we cannot factor it out of their entry points. The 1 warmup + 3 measured-run protocol discards the warmup; the median over the three measured runs is reported, with q_{25} and q_{75} recorded for variability checks.

Synthetic-data seeds. Quest-style synthetic datasets are re-generated from fixed seeds (one seed per dataset, recorded in the artifact archive); regenerating from the same seeds reproduces the exact (t, i) stream byte-for-byte. Real datasets are used unmodified except for the preprocessing described in §4.3.

Artifact. Source code, raw run logs, aggregated benchmark CSVs, dataset-preprocessing scripts, and synthetic-data generator parameters are released in the GitHub repository at <https://github.com/swetmr/fastapriori>; the commit corresponding to the submitted results is tagged. Reproducing the headline tables takes ~8 h on a single c3-highmem-8 VM (one full sweep); spot-checking a single (dataset, method, k , s) cell takes < 10 s for fast methods and up to 25 min for the slowest-completed cells.